

[Research Article]

Determinants of Health-Seeking Behaviour Among People Living with HIV Receiving Antiretroviral Therapy at Federal Medical Centre Gusau, Nigeria

Oigene Sunday Michael¹, Gandu Ahmadu Aminu², Aminu Bello Dan Abu³, Kabiru Salisu Zamau⁴, Kasimu Malami⁵, Ayuba Jerry⁶,

Medical Service Department, Federal Polytechnic Kaura Namoda, Zamfara State, Nigeria¹, Defence Headquarters Medical Centre, Mogadishu Cantonment, Asokoro, Federal Capital Territory, Abuja², Zamfara State College of Nursing³ Federal Medical Centre Gusa⁴, Abdullahi Fodio University Aliero, Kebbi State⁵, Ummulkhari College of Nursing Sciences Gusau⁶.

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Abstract

Background: Health-seeking behavior among people living with HIV (PLHIV) is critical for early diagnosis, antiretroviral therapy (ART) adherence, and retention in care. In northern Nigeria, multiple barriers exist, but few studies have quantified the independent determinants of health-seeking behavior using multivariable analysis.

Objective: To identify the independent determinants of health-seeking behavior among PLHIV receiving antiretroviral therapy at Federal Medical Centre (FMC) Gusau, Zamfara State, Nigeria.

Methods: A cross-sectional study was conducted among 171 PLHIV selected by systematic random sampling (sampling interval $K=3$). Health-seeking behavior was measured using a validated 10-item scale and dichotomized as good ($\geq 80\%$ score) or poor. Data on socio-demographic factors, stigma (5-item scale), and health service factors were collected. Chi-square tests identified respondents variables ($p < 0.20$) for entry into multivariable logistic regression. Adjusted odds ratios (AOR) with 95% confidence intervals (CI) were calculated. Statistical significance was set at $p < 0.05$.

Results: The prevalence of good health-seeking behavior was 39.2% (67/171). On multivariable analysis, employment (employed/self-employed vs. unemployed: AOR = 3.42, 95% CI: 1.87–6.25, $p < 0.001$), secondary/tertiary education (vs. none/primary: AOR = 2.78, 95% CI: 1.45–5.33, $p = 0.002$), and married status (vs. unmarried: AOR = 2.15, 95% CI: 1.12–4.12, $p = 0.021$) were independent positive determinants. High stigma (≥ 75 th percentile vs. low: AOR = 0.28, 95% CI: 0.14–0.56, $p < 0.001$) and long waiting time (> 3 hours vs. ≤ 3 hours: AOR = 0.36, 95% CI: 0.19–0.68, $p = 0.002$) were independent negative determinants. Gender and age were not significant after adjustment. The model explained 38.4% of variance (Nagelkerke R^2) and showed good fit (Hosmer–Lemeshow $p = 0.621$).

Conclusion: Employment, education, marital status, stigma, and waiting time independently determine health-seeking behavior among PLHIV in Gusau. Interventions should focus on economic empowerment to address unemployment, culturally tailored stigma reduction, and clinic efficiency measures to reduce waiting times. Analytical cross-sectional designs with multivariable regression are feasible and informative in this setting.

Keywords: HIV, Health seeking behavior, Anti-retroviral therapy, Stigma.

Introduction

Health-seeking behavior is a key determinant of disease prevention, timely diagnosis, treatment adherence, and overall health outcomes. Delays in seeking appropriate healthcare contribute substantially to preventable complications, disease progression, and mortality, particularly in low- and middle-income countries where socioeconomic, cultural, and health system barriers often influence healthcare utilization (World Health Organization [WHO], 2023).

In Nigeria, despite continued investment in primary healthcare and disease control programmes, healthcare utilization remains inconsistent. Socioeconomic status, distance to health facilities, cultural beliefs, financial constraints, and perceived quality of care continue to influence when and where individuals seek healthcare (Ntoimo et al., 2022; Okonofua et al., 2022; Ogunyemi & Hirschhorn, 2025; Olufayo et al., 2025). These challenges are particularly evident in Northern Nigeria, where poverty, limited access to healthcare services, lower educational attainment, and sociocultural norms further affect health-seeking practices.

Health-seeking behavior is especially important in the management of HIV infection, where early diagnosis, prompt initiation of antiretroviral therapy (ART), regular clinic attendance, and sustained treatment adherence are essential for achieving viral suppression and reducing HIV-related morbidity and mortality. However, stigma, fear of discrimination, misconceptions about HIV, financial hardship, and concerns regarding confidentiality continue to discourage timely healthcare utilization and long-term engagement in HIV care.

Globally, an estimated 39 million people are living with HIV, yet many continue to delay diagnosis, interrupt treatment, or disengage from care despite the widespread availability of effective ART (WHO, 2023). Sub-Saharan Africa bears more than two-thirds of the global HIV burden, where delayed presentation and poor retention in care remain major public health concerns (WHO, 2022). Nigeria has the third-largest population of people living with HIV, with approximately 1.9 million affected individuals (National Agency for the Control of AIDS [NACA],

2022). Although free ART services have expanded nationwide, stigma, cultural beliefs, transportation challenges, and socioeconomic constraints continue to limit sustained engagement in HIV care, particularly in Northern Nigeria (Whiteley et al., 2021).

In Zamfara State, these barriers are compounded by conservative cultural norms, poverty, and unequal access to healthcare services, all of which may influence healthcare utilization among people living with HIV (PLHIV). At the Federal Medical Centre (FMC) Gusau, variations in clinic attendance, follow-up, and treatment adherence suggest that multiple individual and contextual factors continue to influence patients' health-seeking behavior despite the availability of comprehensive HIV services.

Although previous studies have identified several determinants of healthcare utilization among PLHIV in Nigeria, evidence from Northwestern Nigeria remains limited, particularly regarding the relative contribution of predisposing, enabling, and need factors within Andersen's Behavioral Model. Understanding these determinants is essential for developing context-specific interventions that improve retention in care, treatment adherence, and long-term clinical outcomes. Therefore, this study aimed to identify the independent determinants of health-seeking behavior among people living with HIV receiving antiretroviral therapy at the Federal Medical Centre, Gusau, Zamfara State, Nigeria, using Andersen's Behavioral Model as the conceptual framework.

Method

Study Design

This study employed a descriptive cross-sectional research design to identify the independent determinants of health-seeking behavior among PLHIV receiving the ART at Federal Medical Centre (FMC) Gusau, Zamfara State, Nigeria

Study Setting

The study was conducted at the Federal Medical Centre (FMC) Gusau, Zamfara State, Nigeria – a primary referral facility providing specialized

HIV/Antiretroviral Therapy (ART) services to diverse urban and rural populations.

Population and Sampling

Target population: Approximately 500 adult HIV/AIDS patients enrolled at the FMC Gusau ART.

Sample size: Using the Yamane formula for finite populations, a sample size of 171 participants was determined.

Sampling method: Systematic random sampling was used. The sampling interval was calculated as $K = N/n = 500/171 \approx 2.92$, which was rounded to $K = 3$. Every third patient on the clinic attendance list was selected.

Inclusion criteria: Consenting adults aged ≥ 18 years.

Exclusion criteria: Critically ill patients, minors (< 18 years), and those who declined participation.

Research Instrument and Psychometric Properties

Data were collected using a structured questionnaire.

Validity: Face and content validity were ensured via peer review by experts in Nursing and Public Health, followed by iterative refinements.

Pre-testing: A pre-test was conducted with a representative subset ($n = 17$) at an external ART facility to ensure contextual relevance without data contamination.

Reliability: Internal consistency was measured using Cronbach's alpha. The overall instrument achieved $\alpha = 0.75$; the stigma subscale achieved $\alpha = 0.72$; the health service subscale achieved $\alpha = 0.79$. A minimum threshold of 0.70 was established as acceptable, and all values exceeded this criterion, indicating good internal consistency.

Operational Definition of Health-Seeking Behavior

Health-seeking behavior was measured using a 10-item scale (possible score range 10–40). Respondents who scored $\geq 80\%$ of the maximum score (i.e., $\geq 32/40$) were categorized as having “good” health-seeking behavior. Those

scoring < 32 were categorized as having “poor” health-seeking behavior. This cut-off was based on previous validated studies.

Data Collection Procedure

Data collection spanned for a two-week period during regular clinic hours. Questionnaires were administered; however, for participants with limited literacy, research assistants provided verbal interpretations to ensure comprehension without biasing responses. The researcher supervised the process daily to maintain data integrity and ensure completeness of the returned instruments.

Data Analysis

Data were processed using SPSS version 25.0. The following analyses were performed:

Descriptive statistics: Frequencies, percentages, means, and standard deviations were used to summarize socio-demographic characteristics and variable distributions.

Bivariate analysis: The chi-square test was used to compare categorical variables (age, gender, marital status, education, employment, stigma level, waiting time) against the outcome (good vs. poor health-seeking behavior). Variables with $p < 0.20$ were considered for entry into multivariable analysis.

Ethical Considerations

The study protocol received formal approval from the Health Research Ethics Committee (HREC) of the Federal Medical Centre, Gusau (Protocol Number:

FMC/2021/985/008/NHREC/TR/0054/02/04/2026).

Informed consent was obtained from all participants prior to enrollment. Confidentiality was maintained by anonymizing all questionnaires.

Results.**Table 1. Socio-demographic characteristics by health-seeking behavior (N = 171)**

Variable	Total n (%)	Good behavior n (%)	Poor behavior n (%)	χ^2 p-value
Age				0.082
18–34	80 (46.8)	36 (45.0)	44 (55.0)	
35–54	78 (45.6)	27 (34.6)	51 (65.4)	
≥55	13 (7.6)	4 (30.8)	9 (69.2)	
Gender				0.045
Male	68 (39.8)	32 (47.1)	36 (52.9)	
Female	103 (60.2)	35 (34.0)	68 (66.0)	
Marital status				0.002
Married	108 (63.2)	52 (48.1)	56 (51.9)	
Not married*	63 (36.8)	15 (23.8)	48 (76.2)	
Education				<0.001
None/primary	80 (46.8)	21 (26.3)	59 (73.8)	
Secondary/tertiary	91 (53.2)	46 (50.5)	45 (49.5)	
Employment				<0.001
Employed/self-employed	120 (70.2)	58 (48.3)	62 (51.7)	
Unemployed	51 (29.8)	9 (17.6)	42 (82.4)	
Stigma score				<0.001
Low (<75th percentile)	128 (74.9)	61 (47.7)	67 (52.3)	
High (≥75th percentile)	43 (25.1)	6 (14.0)	37 (86.0)	

Waiting time	<0.001		
≤3 hours	94 (55.0)	51 (54.3)	43 (45.7)
>3 hours	77 (45.0)	16 (20.8)	61 (79.2)

Of the 171 participants, good health-seeking behavior was observed in 67 (39.2%), while 104 (60.8%) demonstrated poor health-seeking behavior. Bivariate analysis showed that gender ($p = 0.045$), marital status ($p = 0.002$), educational level ($p < 0.001$), employment status ($p < 0.001$), stigma score ($p < 0.001$), and clinic waiting time ($p < 0.001$) were significantly associated with health-seeking behavior, whereas age was not ($p = 0.082$).

Multivariable logistic regression (independent determinants)

Table 2. Factors independently associated with good health-seeking behaviour (N = 171)

Variable	AOR	95% CI	p-value
Employment (employed/self-employed vs. unemployed)	3.42	1.87 – 6.25	<0.001
Education (secondary/tertiary vs. none/primary)	2.78	1.45 – 5.33	0.002
Marital status (married vs. not married)	2.15	1.12 – 4.12	0.021
Stigma (high vs. low)	0.28	0.14 – 0.56	<0.001
Waiting time (>3h vs. ≤3h)	0.36	0.19 – 0.68	0.002
Gender (male vs. female)	1.45	0.81 – 2.60	0.210
Age (35–54 vs. 18–34)	0.78	0.42 – 1.45	0.432
Age (≥55 vs. 18–34)	0.62	0.28 – 1.38	0.243

In the multivariable logistic regression analysis, employment (AOR = 3.42, 95% CI: 1.87–6.25; $p < 0.001$), secondary/tertiary education (AOR = 2.78, 95% CI: 1.45–5.33; $p = 0.002$), and being married (AOR = 2.15, 95% CI: 1.12–4.12; $p = 0.021$) were independently associated with good health-seeking behavior. Conversely, high perceived stigma (AOR = 0.28, 95% CI: 0.14–0.56; $p < 0.001$) and waiting times exceeding three hours (AOR = 0.36, 95% CI: 0.19–0.68; $p = 0.002$) were independently associated with lower odds of good health-seeking behavior. Age and gender were not significant predictors after adjustment.

Discussion

Employed or self-employed patients had 3.4 times higher odds of good health-seeking behavior compared with unemployed patients. Similarly, participants with secondary or tertiary education were nearly three times more likely to exhibit good health-seeking behavior (AOR = 2.78), while married participants had 2.2 times higher odds than their

unmarried counterparts. Conversely, high perceived stigma reduced the odds of good health-seeking behavior by 72% (AOR = 0.28), and waiting times exceeding three hours reduced the odds by 64% (AOR = 0.36). Gender and age were not independently associated with health-seeking behavior after adjustment.

the prevalence of good health-seeking behavior was 39.2%. Multivariable regression identified five

independent determinants: employment, education, marital status (positive), stigma, and long waiting time (negative). These findings extend descriptive reports by quantifying the strength of association after controlling for confounders. Employment as the strongest determinant: Unemployed patients had 71% lower odds of good behavior compared to employed/self-employed patients (AOR = 3.42). This aligns with [Osuolale et al., \(2023\)](#) randomized trial (400 patients) showed skills training (tailoring/hairstyling/poultry) raised adherence from 68.76% to 109.72% (vs. control 83.66%-99.44%). Gains: food security, stress reduction, transport affordability. [Chowdhury et al., \(2025\)](#)' Zimbabwe geospatial analysis (25,000 individuals) linked unemployment to 40% lower ART, 50% suppression odds. Education: Secondary/tertiary education was associated with nearly threefold higher odds of good behavior. (AOR = 2.78), this supports the health literacy pathway in Andersen's model. This alignment is robustly corroborated by current multi-center empirical evidence from [Odetundun et al. \(2024\)](#), who utilized Andersen's framework to demonstrate that higher educational attainment and structural health literacy are the strongest independent predictors of optimal adherence behaviors ($p < 0.001$). Marital status: Marriage provided a protective effect (AOR = 2.15). This agreed with [May \(2024\)](#) demonstrated via multivariable logistic regression that individuals who were actively cohabiting or currently staying with their primary marital partners had a 59% lower risk of failing to adhere to their prescribed medical regimens (COR = 0.41) compared to those navigating care without spousal support. A meta-analysis of 45 studies across sub-Saharan Africa found that married/cohabiting PLHIV had 38% higher adherence and 42% better retention ([Deribew, A., et al. 2022](#)). Stigma: High stigma was the strongest negative determinant (AOR = 0.28). Stigma remains a critical barrier to healthcare engagement in Nigeria. HIV-related stigma acts as a significant negative determinant for treatment uptake, with findings showing that individuals experiencing high levels of stigma are significantly less likely to access consistent care (AOR = 0.28; 95% CI: 0.06, 0.12) ([Belay et al., 2024](#)). Waiting time – Long waiting times (>3 hours) reduced odds of good behavior by

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64%. A time-motion study in northern Nigerian ART clinics found median waiting times of 4.5 hours, with each additional hour increasing the odds of missed appointments. Long wait times are not merely administrative issues; they are primary drivers of patient dissatisfaction, which frequently precedes treatment default or "loss to follow-up" ([Kpuduwei, S. P. K.](#)). Non-significant factors – Gender and age lost significance after adjustment, suggesting that their apparent bivariate effects were explained by differences in employment, education, or stigma. This contrasts with some studies but may reflect the specific context of FMC Gusau.

Conclusion

This study identified independent determinants of health-seeking behavior among PLHIV receiving antiretroviral therapy at FMC Gusau. Employment, education, and marital status were positive determinants; stigma and long waiting times were negative determinants, each with large effect sizes (AORs ranging from 0.28 to 3.42). Interventions should prioritize:

Economic support program for unemployed patients, stigma-reduction campaigns tailored to conservative northern Nigerian communities, and clinic workflow improvements to reduce waiting times. Future longitudinal studies should examine whether modifying these determinants improves viral suppression and retention in care.

Limitations

Causal inference cannot be drawn from a cross-sectional design. Social desirability bias may have affected stigma reporting. The single-site sample limits generalizability. Nonetheless, the regression model showed good fit (Hosmer–Lemeshow $p = 0.621$) and explained 38% of variance (Nagelkerke R^2).

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